

Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and antimicrobial studies of oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with NNS donor tridentate Schiff base ligands

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Abstract : The reactions of diacetylmonoxime with thiosemicarbazide and morpholine N-thiohydrazide produce two different tridentate Schiff base ligands. Using these ligands some dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes have been synthesized. The newly isolated complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements by Rast's method, magnetic moments, molar conductance and other usual spectroscopic data. The ligands and their dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes have also been screened for *in vitro* antimicrobial activity against bacteria (*Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and fungi (*Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*). The complexes were found to be more potent as compared to the ligands and the oxo-complex are also found to be more active than dioxo-species.

Keywords : Schiff base, molybdenum, complex, spectroscopy, antibacterial, antifungal.

Introduction

Molybdenum having stable and variable oxidation states has been found to play a number of important roles in the biological world^{1,2}. Different enzymes like aldehyde oxidase, xanthine oxidase, xanthine dehydrogenase, nitrate reductase etc. contain molybdenum in their active site and often called as oxomolybdenum enzymes^{3,4}. In recent years much attention has been focused on the molybdenum chelates, since many molybdenum(V) and molybdenum(VI) complexes have been found to act as simple models for biochemical reactions⁵ and in nitrogenase enzymes⁶. Molybdenum complexes are reported to show efficient catalytic activity in the reactions like epoxidation of olefins, ammoxidation and olefin metathesis⁷⁻¹⁰. In continuation of our earlier work on the transition metal complexes of hydrazides, hydrazones, thiohydrazides and thiohydrazones¹¹, we have studied the complexation reactions of H₂L and H₂L' with MoO₂(acac)₂, Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O,

(NH₄)₂[MoOCl₅] and (PyH)₂[Mo(SCN)₆] leading to the syntheses of many new dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes.

Results and discussion

Syntheses :

The reactions of diacetylmonoximethiosemicarbazone (H₂L) and diacetylmonoximemorpholine-N-thiohydrazone (H₂L') with MoO₂(acac)₂, Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, (NH₄)₂⁻[MoOCl₅] and (PyH)₂[Mo(SCN)₆] under varied reaction conditions yielded eight new dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes (1)-(8) (Scheme 1). The characterization data of the complexes are summarized in Table 1 which supports the formulation of the complexes. Unfortunately, no single crystals of the complexes could be grown in spite of our best efforts.

Molecular weight, molar conductance and magnetic moments :

The molecular weights (Table 1) of some of the com-

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Scheme 1. Reactions of the ligands with metal salts leading to the synthesis of metal complexes.

Scheme 2. Preparation of the ligand system ($\text{H}_2\text{L}'$).

pounds, measured by Rast's method, are also in good agreement with these formulations. The molar conductance values (Table 1) of the isolated complexes measured

in DMSO and DMF are found within the range of 9.20–15.10 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ of 10^{-3}M solution, suggest their non-electrolytic nature¹².

Table 1. Characterization data of dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Δ_M^a ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff}^b B.M.
				C	H	N	Cl	Mo		
1.	$\text{H}_2\text{L}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{OS})$	Yellow	– (174)	33.96 (34.48)	5.03 (5.74)	31.82 (32.18)	–	–	–	–
2.	$\text{H}_2\text{L}'(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S})$	Yellow	– (244)	44.29 (44.26)	6.38 (6.6)	22.76 (22.95)	–	–	–	–
3.	$[(\text{L})\text{MoO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (1) $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{SMo}$	Brown	300 (318)	18.90 (18.87)	3.62 (3.14)	17.82 (17.61)	–	30.00 (30.19)	15.11	Dia ^c
4.	$[(\text{L}')\text{MoO}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (2) $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SMo}$	Reddish- brown	392 (388)	27.58 (27.83)	4.41 (4.12)	14.28 (14.43)	–	24.68 (24.74)	11.80	Dia ^c
5.	$[(\text{L}')\text{MoO}_2(\text{THF})]$ (3) $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{SMo}$	Yellowish- brown	380 (372)	29.21 (29.03)	4.58 (4.3)	15.18 (15.05)	–	25.90 (25.8)	12.71	Dia ^c
6.	$[(\text{L}')\text{MoO}_2(\text{THF})]$ (4) $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5\text{SMo}$	Yellowish- brown	– (442)	35.59 (35.29)	4.00 (4.07)	12.96 (12.66)	–	21.88 (21.71)	9.2	Dia ^c
7.	$[(\text{L})\text{MoO}(\text{Cl})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (5) $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3\text{SClMo}$	Reddish- brown	340 (337.5)	17.61 (17.77)	2.88 (2.96)	16.64 (16.6)	10.68 (10.5)	28.20 (28.44)	10.00	1.76
8.	$[(\text{L}')\text{MoO}(\text{Cl})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (6) $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{SClMo}$	Reddish- brown	– (407.5)	26.00 (26.5)	4.00 (3.92)	13.52 (13.74)	8.90 (8.71)	23.8 (23.5)	12.80	1.79
9.	$[(\text{L})\text{MoO}(\text{SCN})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (7) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Mo}$	Purple- red	370 (360)	20.28 (20.00)	2.88 (2.78)	19.52 (19.44)	–	26.88 (26.67)	14.50	1.71
10.	$[(\text{L}')\text{MoO}(\text{SCN})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (8) $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{O}_3\text{S}_2\text{Mo}$	Light- brown	– (430)	28.0 (27.90)	3.80 (3.72)	16.33 (16.27)	–	22.80 (22.32)	12.00	1.67

^a 10^{-3} M Solution in DMSO at room temperature; ^bSolid state at room temperature; ^cDiamagnetic.

All the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes (1)–(4) are diamagnetic, while all the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes (5)–(8) are paramagnetic with magnetic moments in the range of 1.67 to 1.79 B.M. at room temperature. These values indicate that there are no significant interactions between neighbouring oxomolybdenum(V) ions in the solid state, but several other analogous oxomolybdenum(V) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes with similar type of tridentate ligands show subnormal magnetic moments^{13,14}.

Infrared and ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands and metal complexes :

The infrared spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes have been recorded. No characteristic absorption assignable to $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ function was found in the ligands (H_2L and $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$), confirming the formation of the Schiff base type ligand. The shift of the imine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band of the oximethiosemicarbazones from 1600 cm^{-1} to $1580\text{--}1570 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the metal complexes indicates coordination of imine nitrogen^{15–17}. Due to loss of proton from $-\text{NH}$ function in thiosemicarbazone moiety in the complexes, an additional $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ absorption is found at higher en-

ergy than $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ of the uncomplexed thiosemicarbazones¹⁸. In this study all the complexes have shown this band within $1622\text{--}1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This is further substantiated by the appearance of azine chromophore¹⁹ ($>\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}<$) around 1600 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the uncoordinated thiosemicarbazone show thioamide IV band, which possesses a considerable contribution from $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$, in the 830 cm^{-1} region. This band shifts to a lower frequency ($50\text{--}80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on coordination of the anionic form of the thiosemicarbazones in agreement with previous studies of the thiosemicarbazones complexes^{20,21}. The $\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$ in the oxime moiety were seen as medium strong bands²² at 1370 cm^{-1} which shifts to the lower frequency suggesting that the oxime group is coordinated through nitrogen atom. The absence of O-H stretching vibrations in the complexes indicates that the oxime $-\text{OH}$ group is deprotonated, though remained free. The $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ bands have been assigned within $350\text{--}360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region confirming the coordination of the sulphur²³ atoms. Thus in these complexes the ligand functions as a dibasic tridentate NNS chelating ligand. The presence of coordinated water mol-

ecule in the complexes (1), (2), (5)-(8) may be inferred by the appearance of bands²⁴ around 3300 and 800 cm⁻¹. On the other hand, complexes (1) and (2) contain *cis*-MoO₂ moiety as supported by the appearance of bands²⁵ in the 890–915 cm⁻¹ region.

The ¹H NMR data for the ligand H₂L and its dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes in DMSO-*d*₆ solution have been measured and analyzed. For the free ligand, the two CH₃ protons gave two singlets at δ 2.10 ppm and δ 2.28 ppm. The NH₂, NH and OH protons appeared as singlet at δ 8.1, 10.32 and 11.78 ppm respectively. For the metal complexes the resonance arising from the oxime hydroxyl proton and NH proton disappear whereas that arising from NH₂ protons are shifted upfield. These observations suggest that the oxime proton (-OH) deprotonated and oxygen bonded to the metal ion. On the other hand thione (C=S) converted to thiol (-SH) and sulphur bonded to the metal ion through deprotonation. The plausible structures are shown in Scheme 1. Thus the ligand H₂L behaves as dibasic tridentate NNS donor.

The complex [(L')MoO₂(H₂O)] (2) does not show any chemical shift due to oxime -OH and -SH protons in DMSO-*d*₆. The methyl protons are observed at δ 2.20 and δ 2.38 ppm, while the methylene protons of the morpholine ring are observed²⁶ at δ 3.35 ppm and δ 3.90 ppm. The complex (2) also exhibits peaks at δ 7.18 ppm (broad) for coordinated water^{27,28}.

Electronic and ESR spectra :

The electronic spectra of dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes show absorption bands of considerably high intensity at about 34500 and 31200 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to ligand to metal charge-transfer^{11,29} transition, possibly superimposed upon other intra-ligand transitions. It seems reasonable to assume that characteristics molybdenyl band does not appear in this region^{11,13}.

The electronic spectra of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes are similar to each other, thereby suggesting a uniform structure for all of them. The complexes are best considered as octahedral with a strong tetragonal distortions resulting from molybdenum-oxygen bonds. The complexes usually exhibit three distinct absorption bands at *ca.* 12500–14000 cm⁻¹, 18000–19500 cm⁻¹ and 21000–29000 cm⁻¹ due to ²B_{2g}→²E (d_{xy} → d_{xz}, d_{yz}), ²B_{2g}→²B_{1g} (d_{xy}→d_{x²-y²) and ²B_{2g}→²A_{1g} (d_{xy}→d_{z²}) crystal field transitions respectively.}

In spite of extensive work much controversy still exists regarding the assignments of the electronic spectra of oxomolybdenum(V) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes^{11,30–35}. The present assignments are, therefore, extremely tentative. The peak formed at *ca.* 13000 cm⁻¹ is possibly associated with ²B_{2g}→²E_g transition. The bands observed in the higher energy region are difficult to assign, but may probably arise from charge-transfer and intra-ligand transitions.

The X-band ESR spectrum of the compound (5), (6), (7) and (8) were measured as powdered sample with DPPH as reference and the given values of the g_{||}, g_⊥ and g_{av} are shown in Table 2. These single line ESR absorption ~3400 G suggest the presence of Mo^V species and the complexes are monomeric in nature having oxomolybdenum(V) at the centre and there is no interaction in the solid state^{36,37}. This is also proved by the absence of any absorption at ~1500 G. Moreover, the complexes (1), (2), (3) and (4) have no unpaired electron and are ESR silent in nature.

Table 2. The ESR parameters of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes

Complex	g	g _⊥	g _{av}
[(L)MoO(Cl)(H ₂ O)] (5)	1.9326	1.9102	1.9196
[(L')MoO(Cl)(H ₂ O)] (6)	1.9331	1.9096	1.9203
[(L)MoO(SCN)(H ₂ O)] (7)	1.9351	1.9053	1.9187

Antimicrobial activities :

The Schiff base ligands and its oxo- and dioxomolybdenum complexes have been tested for antimicrobial activities following previously published methods^{38,39} against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* as Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria respectively and antifungal screening activity against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The zones of inhibition caused by the bioactive complexes were measured and the results are given in Table 3. The comparative study shows that the complexes have been found to be more active than the corresponding Schiff base ligand and it may be attributed to chelation theory^{40–43}. Moreover, the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes also show higher activity than the dioxo-complexes. Within the chelated metal complexes the polarity of the metal ions are greatly reduced due to overlapping with the ligand orbitals and the delocalization of the electrons over the whole complex is also observed as well. These two factors are res-

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of the ligands and dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes

Complex	Growth inhibition zone diameter (in mm)			
	1 mg/mL		1 mg/mL	
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>
Control DMSO	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a	0.0 ^a
H ₂ L(C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS)	4 ^a	5 ^a	5 ^a	5 ^a
H ₂ L'(C ₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S)	6 ^a	8 ^a	7 ^a	6 ^a
[(L)MoO ₂ (H ₂ O)] (1)	11 ^a	10 ^a	9 ^a	8 ^a
[(L')MoO ₂ (H ₂ O)] (2)	14 ^b	15 ^b	13 ^b	14 ^b
[(L')MoO ₂ (THF)] (3)	16 ^b	17 ^c	15 ^b	17 ^c
[(L')MoO ₂ (THF)] (4)	14 ^b	15 ^b	12 ^b	12 ^b
[(L)MoO(Cl)(H ₂ O)] (5)	18 ^c	16 ^b	14 ^b	16 ^b
[(L')MoO(Cl)(H ₂ O)] (6)	31 ^c	29 ^c	22 ^c	20 ^c
[(L)MoO(SCN)(H ₂ O)] (7)	17 ^c	15 ^b	14 ^b	16 ^b
[(L')MoO(SCN)(H ₂ O)] (8)	28 ^c	27 ^c	20 ^b	16 ^b

^aInactive; ^bFairly active; ^cDecidedly active.

Fig. 2. Thione-thiol inter conversion of the ligands.

possible for making the metal complexes suitable for enhanced penetration into the lipid membranes and thus the bioavailability of the metal-therapeutics helps to block the

Fig. 3. ESR spectrum of complex (5).

metal binding sites as well in the enzymes of microorganisms. Thus, by blocking the synthesis of the proteins, the complexes actually inhibit the growth of the microorganisms⁴⁴. The higher activity of oxomolybdenum(V) complexes may be attributed to their high lipid solubility, volume and pharmacokinetic factors which play the pivotal roles in concluding the efficacy of such antibacterial agents.

Experimental

Physical measurements :

The elemental analyses were carried out on Elementar Vario EL III, Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzers at the SAIF, Lucknow. The electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded on a Hitachi 200-20 and Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometers and infrared spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 and L120-000A FTIR spectrophotometers. The molar conductance (10^{-3} M in DMSO and DMF) was measured using an Elico conductivity bridge. The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Guoy method. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's method⁴⁵.

Materials :

The solvents and chemicals were purified and dried prior to use by standard procedures. Diacetylmonoxime and thiosemicarbazide were purchased from SRL, Mumbai. Morpholine N-thiohydrazide was prepared in the laboratory as described⁴⁶ earlier.

Preparation of the ligands :

Preparation of H_2L : A methanolic solution (15 ml) of diacetylmonoxime (0.50 g, 0.005 mol) was added to a solution (15 ml) thiosemicarbazide (0.46 g, 0.005 mol) in the same solvent and then the solution mixture was refluxed for ~2 h. The resulting solution on concentration and cooling yielded a yellow powdery compound. It was filtered off, washed with cold methanol and dried *in vacuo*.

Preparation of H_2L' : To a hot ethanolic solution (15 ml) of morpholine N-thiohydrazide (0.8 g, 0.005 mol) was added diacetylmonoxime (0.5 g, 0.005 mol) in dry ethanol. The solution mixture was then refluxed for 2 h and then upon concentration and cooling a yellowish gummy mass was obtained. No solid compound was separated.

To isolate the solid ligand the above reaction was modified earlier in our laboratory⁴⁶ but the reaction actually afforded a new nitrogen-sulfur zwitterionic heterocyclic compound, N-(3,4-dimethyl-1,2,5-thiadiazole-2-ium-2-yl)morpholine-4-carbothioate, instead of the desired simple Schiff base ligand H_2L' (Scheme 2).

The crystal structure of the nitrogen-sulfur zwitter-ionic heterocyclic compound has also been solved (CCDC 721752) and already reported⁴⁶ by our group as given in Fig. 1.

As the ligand H_2L' could not be isolated in the solid phase, so the reactions involving this ligand H_2L' have been carried out under *in situ* condition.

Syntheses of the complexes :

Syntheses of $[(L)MoO_2(H_2O)]$ (1) and $[(L')MoO_2(H_2O)]$ (2) :

A solution of $Na_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ (2.42 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was mixed with a solution of the ligand H_2L (0.01 mol) or with the components of the ligand H_2L' (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml). The pH of the solution was adjusted to ~6 and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h and filtered while hot. From the filtrate the brown crystalline product (1) or reddish-brown compound (2)

was obtained on cooling. It was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 70%.

Syntheses of $[(L)MoO_2(THF)]$ (3) and $[(L')MoO_2(THF)]$ (4) :

The hot dry ethanol solution of H_2L (0.01 mol) or the solution of the components of the ligand H_2L' (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of $MoO_2(acac)_2$ (3.26 g, 0.01 mol) in mixed solvent EtOH : THF (50 : 50, v/v, 25 ml) and refluxed gently for 3 h and filtered while hot. The filtrate gave a solid yellowish-brown compound on concentration and cooling, yield 70% for both the compounds.

Syntheses of $[(L)MoO(H_2O)Cl]$ (5) and $[(L')MoO(H_2O)Cl]$ (6) :

The solution of $(NH_4)_2[MoOCl_5]$ (2.54 g, 0.01 mol) in mixed solvents EtOH : MeOH (50 : 50, v/v, 40 ml) was allowed to react with a solution of the ligand H_2L (0.03 mol) or with the components of the ligand H_2L' (0.03 mol) in the same solvent system (40 ml) at room temperature. On thorough stirring these reddish-brown complexes (5) and (6) were precipitated in about 70% yield.

Syntheses of $[(L)MoO(H_2O)(SCN)]$ (7) and $[(L')MoO(H_2O)(SCN)]$ (8) :

A solution of $(PyH)_2[Mo(SCN)_6]$ (6.04 g, 0.01 mol) in EtOH : MeOH (50 : 50, v/v, 30 ml) was mixed with a solution of the ligand H_2L (0.03 mol) or with the components of the ligand H_2L' (0.03 mol) in the same mixed solvent (40 ml) at room temperature. On thorough stirring a purple-red (7) and light-brown (8) solid compound were separated out which were collected by filtration and washed with methanol and dried *in vacuo*, yield 65%.

Conclusion

Some mononuclear dioxomolybdenum(VI) and oxomolybdenum(V) complexes with the two new thione type ligands have been synthesized and properly characterized with the help of different physicochemical techniques. Both the ligands act as dibasic tridentate NNS donor system. The spectroscopic data shows that all the molybdenum complexes adopt a distorted octahedral geometry. The complexes are capable of functioning as active antimicrobial agents and the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes are found to be less active than the oxomolybdenum(V) complexes.

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